

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE WORKING TEMPERATURES OF A GENERATOR SET POWERED BY A DIESEL – JATROPHA OIL BLEND

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ABSTRACT

In this work, mathematical models were developed to correlate the working temperatures of a diesel engine with the load and the oil content of Jatropha curcas in diesel. A Lister Petter indirect injection engine was used and a blend of diesel with 5 and 10% jatropha oil. A Factorial Design was used to plan the experiments and the Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to develop the correlations. The models obtained are used to predict the temperatures of the exhaust gases of the cylinders and the temperatures of the coolant at the inlet and outlet of the radiator. The JCO content in the fuel did not cause significant changes in exhaust gas or coolant temperatures. The diesel mixture with 10% Jatropha curcas vegetable oil does not produce changes in the thermal behavior of the engine, so it can be used directly in this type of engine without making any modifications.

KEYWORDS

Engine, Renewable energy, Vegetable oil, Load.

1. INTRODUCTION

The energy consumption is increasing day by day with industrialization and with the constant growth of the world population [1]. In turn, the air pollution of the planet is a serious problem that grows considerably over the years and is largely related to energy production. This pollution is caused by the use of fossil fuels in transportation and generation of electricity sectors [2]. Internal combustion engines (ICEs) are the most widely used equipment for these purposes. Diesel engine plays a dominant role in: heavy vehicles, agricultural machinery, engineering machinery, power production and other fields due to its high energy efficiency and good economic characteristics [3].

Manufacturers of ICEs and scientists involved in this area of knowledge have been researching, designing and testing alternative technologies that provide sufficient power while remaining within regulatory gas emission limits [2]. Some of these new alternatives have been: the use of oils of vegetable origin and their derivatives as fuels, the use of emulsions, hydrogen, alcohol, nanoparticles and other additives [4-8].

Researching engine performance and emissions experimentally for the evaluation of new technologies is complex, time-consuming and expensive [2]. For the development of these researches it is necessary to carry out many experiments, which is why in recent years there has been an increased interest in the use of various types of mathematical models to predict and optimize the behavior and emissions of ICEs [9]. One of the most important advantages of mathematical modeling is that its application minimizes processing time and cost, by reducing the need to perform countless and complex experimental work [10].

A mathematical model is nothing more than the representation that characterizes a physical system or process, which can be obtained in two ways: strictly theoretical (theoretical modeling) and experimentally, based on real input and output data from the system (experimental modeling). The main advantage of process modeling is that it allows predicting the dynamic and static behavior of systems before building them and analyzing the performance of an existing one in order to study its behavior. Furthermore, using modeling does not expose the process to damage and can determine what might happen to it by simulating the model with an unusual input condition or disturbance.

When it comes to evaluating technologies and predicting the behavior of an ICE the most important parameters have been: fuel consumption, gas emissions, efficiency, pressure in the combustion chamber, torque, effective power, ignition delay, among others. Various researchers have tried to predict these parameters and for this they have mainly used the response surface methodology [11].

In 2015 Dhole et al. presented mathematical models of some experimental research carried out for different combinations of gas and diesel under a wide range of load conditions for a turbocharged four-cylinder diesel engine. The response variables considered in this work were the brake thermal efficiency, the emissions of unburned hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide and nitrogen oxides [12].

On the other hand, Sarvestani et al. researched the use of mathematical models to predict the specific fuel consumption and exhaust gas emissions of a diesel engine as a function of the load and the volume of magnetic nanoparticles of Fe_3O_4 contained in the fuel. Regression analysis was performed using the experimental data. The experiments were carried out with nanoparticle concentrations of 0.4 and 0.8% by volume. These researchers used a variable load direct injection diesel engine. The predicted values obtained by the regression equations were compared with the values obtained from the experimental measurements. Regression adjusted models were able to predict specific fuel consumption and emission characteristics with a correlation coefficient R^2 in the range of 94-98% [11].

Several studies about the influence of the use of different types of biodiesel and vegetable oils on gas emissions and fuel consumption of diesel engines have been reported [7, 13, 14]. In addition to the gas emissions and fuel consumption of an ICE, heat transfer is an important requirement. In the analysis, development and design of the internal combustion engine, the temperatures of the system are directly related to its efficiency and to the levels of contamination that these engines generates [15]. However, there are few reports on the influence of the use of this type of fuel on the working temperatures of an engine.

From the point of view of mathematical modeling, temperature has been one of the least studied parameters for its prediction and optimization from experimental data. That is why the objective of this work is to obtain a mathematical model from experimental results that allows predicting the working temperatures of an indirect injection diesel engine, depending on the load and the

content of crude oil of *Jatropha curcas* added to the diesel, from the response surface methodology.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Fuel Properties

The fuels used were Diesel and crude vegetable oil from *Jatropha curcas* L. For the tests carried out on the combustion engine, a diesel-oil blend of *Jatropha curcas* L. crude oil at 5 and 10% of the latter was used. The main properties of these fuels and the methodology followed for the preparation of the blend can be found in [6].

2.2. Engine Test Bench

A Lister Petter LPWS2, two-cylinder, indirect injection diesel engine was used for the tests. The motor has a rigid connection coupled to an electric generator. The main characteristics of the motor and the generator are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Technical specifications of the engine and generator.

Engine		Generator	
Cylinder diameter (mm)	86	Maker	Lister Petter
Stroke (mm)	80	Model	BC1164D1
Displacement (L)	0,930	Power factor	0,86
Compression ratio	23,5:1	Tension (V)	220
Constant speed(rpm)	1500	Speed (rpm)	1500
Cooling type	Water	Frequency (Hz)	50

The load is applied by means of a system of electrical resistances that are connected to the generator, these when they are turned on consume energy, causing the different loads in which the engine works. The engine load can vary from 0 to 96% in a range of 16% load.

Another element of the experimental installation is the control panel, in this are located most of the instruments that allow to control and measure the parameters of the generator set, among these is the temperature control panel. The motor has a series of thermocouples installed that allow the behavior of some of the main operating temperatures to be analyzed in real time. A diagram of the experimental installation with the location of the thermocouples and the analyzed temperatures is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scheme of the experimental installation used.

In each experimental run and to determine the working temperatures of the engine, the fuel feed system was initially cleaned and sweetened, to later fill the tanks with the fuel to be used in each run. Then the engine was started until it reached the optimum working temperature, coolant at the radiator outlet ($T4 = 84^{\circ}\text{C}$) and it was waited (approximately five minutes) until the main engine parameters stabilized.

The current generator was then activated to start feeding the load bank. To begin providing the load to the motor, two resistors from the load bank were connected to the system and five minutes were waited for the different motor parameters to stabilize. At this time the readings of all temperatures were made in the Control Panel. The load bank is made up of 12 electric resistances that are connected in pairs so that six different loads are applied to the motor.

2.3. Experimental Design

To carry out the experiments and for their subsequent analysis, a multilevel factorial design with two factors was used: the engine load (Load) and the crude oil content of jatropha curcas L. used in the fuel (JCO). The levels selected for each factor were six and three respectively. The ranges and levels of the independent variables are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Design factors and their corresponding variation levels.

Factors	Units	Levels					
		16	32	48	64	80	96
Load	%	16	32	48	64	80	96
JCO	%	0		5		10	

According to the factorial design used, $6 * 3 = 18$ experiments should be performed. Each experiment was repeated three times to ensure the repeatability of the results, in addition the experiments on the engine were performed randomly. T1 was kept at $32 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. The response variables analyzed with RSM in the experimental design were:

- T2: Exhaust gas temperature of cylinder # 1 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- T3: Exhaust gas temperature of cylinder # 2 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- T4: Temperature of the cooling liquid at the radiator inlet ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

- T5: Temperature of the coolant at the outlet of the radiator or heat exchanger (°C).

The response surface methodology (RSM) is composed of a group of mathematical and statistical models in which the response of interest depends on different significant variables, and the objective of the method is to model and optimize this response [16]. To achieve this goal, a linear or square polynomial equation is established to define the case study.

In most of the publications that use RSM, the equations that relate the responses to the independent variables are not reported. That is why the first step to apply the RSM is to find an approximation function between the inputs and the outputs of the analyzed process [9]. In most cases, RSM uses a low-order polynomial as a mathematical model. When the relationship between the parameters is linear, the approximation function is a first-order model or polynomial (1). If the relationship between the parameters is not linear then it fits a second order polynomial (2).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i X_i + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i_1 > j}^k \sum_{j}^k \beta_{ij} X_i X_j + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where Y is the response variable (T2, T3, T4 and T5), X_i and X_j are the independent variables (Load and JCO), β_i is the linear coefficient, β_{ii} is the quadratic coefficient, β corresponds to the regression coefficients, k is the number of factors studied in the experiment and ε is a random experimental error, which is assumed to have a mean equal to zero [17].

Analysis of variance (ANOVA), Fisher's statistical test (F test) and p-value <0.5 (indicates that the parameter is significant with a 95% confidence level) were used to verify the statistical significance of the individual parameters in each response variable.

To evaluate the quality of the fit of the models proposed by RSM, the statistical parameters Correlation coefficient (R²), Adjusted correlation coefficient (R²adj) and the mean absolute error (MAE) were used.

Statistical analyzes and mathematical models were performed using the statistical program Statgraphics Centurion XV version 15.2.14 (StatPointTechnologies Inc.), the response surface graphs were performed with the MATLAB R2018a program version 9.4.0.813654 (MathWorks Inc.).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Analysis of the Models

The RSM proposed a correlation of the response variables (in this case the working temperatures of the engine) with the factors of the design used (JCO and Load). The second order polynomials (quadratic models) were the ones that best explained the variation and dependence of the variables because they had the best R², R²adj and MAE fits. The mathematical models obtained for T2, T3, T4 and T5 are presented in equations (3) - (6) respectively.

$$T2 = 148,625 + 1,129*Load + 0,302*JCO + 5,88 \times 10^{-3} * Load^2 - 4,8 \times 10^{-3} * Load * JCO \quad (3)$$

$$T3 = 156,24 + 1,299*Load + 0,098*JCO + 4,742 \times 10^{-3} * Load^2 - 2,995 \times 10^{-3} * Load * JCO \quad (4)$$

$$T4 = 83,898 + 0,019*Load - 0,011*JCO + 0,032 \times 10^{-3} * Load^2 - 0,118 \times 10^{-3} * Load * JCO \quad (5)$$

$$T5 = 25,723 + 0,071*Load - 0,032*JCO - 0,194 \times 10^{-3} * Load^2 - 0,866 \times 10^{-3} * Load * JCO \quad (6)$$

The R^2 is an indicator that determines the quality of the fit of the experimental data with the model proposed with the use of RSM. It is preferred that the difference between R^2 and R^2_{adj} is less than 0.2. Low MAE values indicate the precision of the prediction techniques when comparing predicted versus observed values. The values of R^2 , R^2_{adj} and MAE obtained for each model are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Statistical parameters of the models proposed by RSM.

Models	Equation	R^2	R^2_{adj}	MAE
T2	3	99.978	99.965	0.591
T3	4	99.982	99.972	0.539
T4	5	94.549	91.434	0.132
T5	6	98.993	98.418	0.123

The high values in the coefficients R^2 and R^2_{adj} , as well as the low MAE values of the obtained models reveal that the regression models describe the experimental data with high levels of reliability.

The quality of the proposed quadratic models can also be assessed by analysis of variance, which is based on the "F value" and the "P value". In general, the pattern of interactions between different parameters can be identified by considering the F value and the P value. It should be noted that the higher the F value and the lower the P value, the corresponding variables are more significant and important in the model [18]. A P value lower than 0.05 means that the analyzed factor is statistically significant on the response variable, with a confidence level of 95%. Table 4 shows the results of the analysis of variance of the response variables studied.

Table 4. Results of the analysis of variance

Source	T2		T3	
	F value	P value	F value	P value
Load	30934.30	0	38703.94	0
JCO	0.36	0.566	1.92	0.209
Load ²	187.91	0	144.22	0
Load *JCO	5.74	0.051	2.63	0.149
Source	T4		T5	
	F value	P value	F value	P value
Load	118.87	0	609.63	0
JCO	2.33	0.171	66.73	0
Load ²	0.13	0.726	6.29	0.041
Load *JCO	0.08	0.785	5.72	0.048

As the table shows, some of the factors analyzed and their respective interactions are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) for engine temperatures. The linear factor of JCO and its interaction with Load have no statistical significance for T2. However, the quadratic term is significant in the behavior of T2 and in the mathematical model that describes it. In the case of T3, only the linear and quadratic terms of the Load factor are statistically significant for its mathematical model, not for the interaction of the parameters and for the JCO factor. For T4, the quadratic term, the interaction of the factors and the linear term of JCO are not statistically significant. Finally, all the terms, both linear, quadratic and the interaction of the factors are statistically significant for the mathematical model that represents the behavior of T5. When analyzing the F value, it can be seen that the term Load presents the highest values, which is why it is the most important input variable and the factor that most influences the behavior of the engine temperatures analyzed according to the RSM.

By eliminating the terms that did not have statistical significance from the previous mathematical models, the following correlations are obtained:

$$T2 = 148,625 + 1,129*Load + 5,88x10^{-3}*Load^2 \quad (7)$$

$$T3 = 156,24 + 1,299Load + 4,742x10^{-3}*Load^2 \quad (8)$$

$$T4 = 83,898 + 0,019*Load \quad (9)$$

$$T5 = 25,723 + 0.071*Load - 0,032*JCO - 0,194x10^{-3}*Load^2 - 0,866x10^{-3}*Load*JCO \quad (10)$$

3.2. Interaction between Different Operating Parameters

The response surface graphs with the interactions between the independent variables (Load and JCO) and the different response variables (T2, T3, T4 and T5) are shown below in Figures (2) - (6).

3.2.1. Effect of Load And JCO on Engine Cylinder Exhaust Gas Temperatures (T2 And T3)

The effect that Load and JCO have on the exhaust gas temperatures of the engine cylinders (# 1 and # 2) is shown in Figures 2 and 3 respectively.

Figure 2. Graph of response surface of T2 vs Load and JCO.

Figure 3. Graph of response surface of T3 vs Load and JCO.

As can be seen in Figures 2 and 3, the increase in the engine load (Load) causes a considerable increase in the temperatures of the exhaust gases from the engine cylinders (T2 and T3). This is because increasing the load on the engine injects more fuel and air into the combustion chamber to produce more power output. Under these conditions the turbulence of the air inside the chamber improves, therefore, a more homogeneous air-fuel mixture can be obtained inside the combustion chamber [19]. Furthermore, the fuel injection pressure increases with increasing engine load resulting in higher quality of the atomization process and smaller fuel droplets. As a result of the increase in air turbulence and the increase in the quality of the atomization process, the combustion quality is considerably increased [20]. That is why the highest values of T2 and T3 are obtained when the motor works at its maximum load.

On the other hand, it is observed that the content of JCO up to 10% in the Diesel does not cause considerable changes in the temperatures T2 and T3. Crude vegetable oils have high viscosities, low caloric values compared to Diesel and poor fuel atomization [21], however, alternatives have been found such as its use mixed with Diesel up to 20% oil [22]. These mixtures allow the use of these alternative fuels in internal combustion engines without the need for mechanical modifications to the engine. Likewise, several investigations are reported in which engine performance very similar to those obtained when using only pure Diesel is obtained, using mixtures of up to 20% *Jatropha curcas* oil [6, 14, 23, 24]. This type of vegetable oil is environmentally friendly, non-toxic and has the potential to significantly reduce pollution when used in combustion engines [25].

3.2.2. Effect of Load And JCO on the Temperatures of the Coolant at the Outlet and at the Inlet of the Radiator (T4 And T5)

The essential function of the engine's cooling system is to lower the temperature of the elements that make up the combustion chamber, enough so that they maintain their resistance [26]. The cooling liquid, in this case water, is the main responsible for the heat transfer that occurs inside the engine. Determining and studying all the variables that influence the behavior of the coolant temperature is of vital importance to increase the efficiency and durability of these systems. There are very few reports on the behavior of these temperatures when the engine uses crude vegetable oil mixtures (such as *Jatropha curcas*) with Diesel as fuel. The variation of the temperatures of the cooling liquid of the Lister Petter LPWS2 engine with respect to the Load and the JCO is presented in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4. Graph of response surface of T4 vs Load and JCO

Figure 5. Graph of response surface of T5 vs Load and JCO

In the figures it can be seen that with the increase in the load to which the motor is subjected, there is a slight increase in T4 and T5. This result is expected, since with the increase in the load there is an increase in the temperatures inside the combustion chambers, as can be seen in Figures 2 and 3. In addition, with the increase in the load, the fuel intake increases, and the heat generated by friction between the moving parts of the engine is increased. This causes the cooling system to have to dissipate more heat which can cause these slight increases in the temperatures of the coolant at the outlet and at the inlet of the radiator.

The JCO content in the fuel did not cause significant modifications in the behavior of T4 and T5. The use of this mixture did not affect the behavior of the engine cooling system. By keeping the engine cooling system operating under the same conditions as with pure Diesel, it is achieved: avoiding the additional formation of Nitrogen Oxides (NOx), preventing friction wear between the piston and the cylinder lines, among others. This means that despite having a lower caloric value, *Jatropha curcas* oil can be used as a blend and still obtain the same benefits in this type of engine, as several researchers have suggested [27-29].

The use of a diesel blend with 10% crude *Jatropha curcas* oil as fuel in a Lister Petter LPWS2 indirect injection engine did not produce significant effects on its thermal behavior. This is

further evidence that this type of alternative fuels (10% JCO blends) can be used directly as fuel without making modifications to the engine.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the Response Surface Methodology was applied to research the impact of the engine load and the use of a Diesel mixture with 10% *Jatropha curcas* vegetable oil on the thermal behavior of an indirect injection Diesel engine. Mathematical models that characterize the behavior of the main working temperatures of the engine under study were obtained. The design of experiments and the statistical analysis used allowed us to identify that the parameter that most influences the analyzed temperatures was the motor load. As the load increases, the temperatures of the exhaust gases from the engine cylinders increase significantly. The JCO content in the fuel did not cause significant changes in exhaust gas temperatures or coolant temperatures. The Diesel mixture with 10% *Jatropha curcas* vegetable oil does not produce changes in the thermal behavior of the engine, so it can be used directly in this type of engine without any modification.

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